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Global Energy Crisis: Analysis and Assessment of Structural Changes in the Energy Market

KEYWORDS

global energy crisis,
energy structure,
financial contamination,
renewable energy sources,
energy transition policy,
energy consumption,
energy intensity

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The energy crisis can have severe economic consequences, including higher energy prices, increased production costs, and reduced competitiveness. Global economic shifts, population growth, and technological advancements are driving energy demand; dependence on energy imports leaves countries vulnerable to price fluctuations and political risks.

This article aims to identify the role of the 2021-2022 energy crisis as a factor contributing to the new energy structure that will emerge in the coming decades.

Materials and methods. The material consisted of research and analytical reports on energy, climate policy, and sustainable development, published in scientific journals and reports from international organizations. Data for 1965-2022 and literature analysis and statistical data analysis were used.

Results. The authors characterize the concept of energy structure, which refers to a specific period in human history during which the consumption of a particular type of fuel predominated. The prerequisites for forming a new energy structure, based on an increased share of renewable energy sources and hydrogen raw materials in the energy generation structure, are highlighted. The 2021-2022 energy crisis had a significant impact on the natural gas markets in Europe and Asia, leading to increased gas prices and financial strain on the energy industries of various countries.

Conclusion. The global community is currently undergoing a transition in its energy structure, marked by the declining dominance of oil and the growing importance of natural gas and alternative fuel sources. The global energy crisis has accelerated efforts toward energy transition and decarbonization, reinforcing policy shifts aiming to establish a new energy framework grounded in renewable energy and hydrogen-based resources.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of this study stems from the significant economic consequences of the global energy crisis, including rising energy prices, increased production costs, and diminished competitiveness. Global economic shifts, population growth, and technological advancement continue to drive up energy demand. At the same time, dependence on energy imports leaves many countries vulnerable to price volatility and geopolitical risks.

The transition to a multipolar world order triggered numerous turbulent events in the international arena. On a global scale, a confrontation is unfolding between the transnationalization of the economy, fueled by globalization, and the reassertion of national sovereignty. This tension inevitably led to a series of crises, one of the most impactful being the 2021-2022 energy crisis which reached global proportions. It was driven by a post-pandemic rebound in the global economy, following the slowdown caused by COVID-19, and by aggressive energy transition policies adopted by developed nations in favor of renewable energy sources (RES). Rising geopolitical tensions further exacerbated the situation, reducing supply in energy markets, creating shortages in certain resource segments, and contributing to heightened price volatility even as production volumes increased [1].

Overall, such instability creates a slowdown in the global economy and demands thorough investigation from the scientific community to develop strategies for risk mitigation. In this context, the present study analyzes the current state of the global energy market and evaluates structural changes in energy consumption patterns through a historical lens. This dual focus underscores the study's significance.

The objectives of this research are to clarify the concept of the global energy structure, explore its historical evolution, and assess the role of the 2021-2022 energy crisis in reshaping it. The subject of the study is the analysis and evaluation of shifts in the global energy structure; the object is the international energy market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

S. Laakso et al. note that the energy crisis, which began at the end of 2021 and worsened after the war in Ukraine in early 2022, led to the need to conserve energy and adjust household consumption patterns to reduce dependence on Russian energy [2].

E. M. Fazelianov identifies the risk factors that contributed to the unsatisfactory situation in the energy sector, including intense volatility, stock levels, supply imbalances, and political unpredictability [3].

S. V. Zhukov and I. A. Kopytin argue that the European Union, by refusing to conclude long-term contracts for the import of natural gas and opting for the spot market, made itself vulnerable to unpredictable fluctuations in commodity prices. The primary long-term structural shifts in the European gas market were: firstly, an accelerated reorientation towards LNG imports; second, a strengthening of the downward trend in demand; and third, a transition of gas prices to a higher level [4].

S. V. Zhukov & O. B. Reznikova write that the European Commission and industry regulators believe that the fundamental cause of the crisis lies in the insufficient speed of energy transition and are trying to force it through the advanced development of wind and solar generation and mechanisms such as greenhouse gas emissions trading and cross-border carbon regulation [5].

O. Ostapenko et al. assess the prospects for utilizing renewable energy sources as a means of addressing the energy crisis and enhancing environmental safety in Ukraine. The authors outline the prospects for using environmentally friendly, energy-saving technologies that leverage non-traditional and renewable energy sources in Ukraine over the foreseeable future, up to 2060 [6].

O. Ruhnau et al. assess the reaction of small consumers, industrial enterprises, and power plants in Germany, as the country's largest importer of natural gas. The authors found significant gas savings for all consumer groups, although these savings varied in terms of time and size. For example, the industry began to reduce consumption in September 2021, while small consumers began to save significantly only from March 2022 [7].

F. Mandys writes that the Czech Republic was particularly hard hit by the energy crisis, where inflation was almost 17% in February 2023. According to the author, the Czech Republic ranks fourth among the most affected countries in Europe. Pensioners, the poorest families, single parents, and households in the smallest municipalities were identified as the most vulnerable socio-economic groups [8].

Y. Guan et al. write that the energy crisis directly affected household heating and cooling costs and indirectly increased prices for other goods and services. The authors demonstrated that total household spending on electricity increased by 62.6-112.9%, resulting in a 2.7-4.8% rise in household spending [9].

G. M. Huebner et al., analyzing survey data from more than 5 thousand British households, note difficulties in maintaining comfortable heat in the house and difficulties in paying for heating costs [10].

G. Meramveliotakis and M. Manioudis note that the European Union developed a set of tools to address supply and demand issues in the field of energy sustainability. According to the authors, these actions aimed exclusively to reduce energy consumption by households and enterprises, neglecting the problems associated with external energy consumption [11].

H. Lee and J. S. Lee examine the potential for cooperation between the EU and Korea to address energy crises, acknowledging their shared values and opportunities for synergy in the energy transition at both bilateral and multilateral levels [12].

M. Farghali et al. offer green alternatives to fossil fuels, including boilers and biofuel stoves, hybrid heat pumps, and solar heat systems. According to the authors, artificial intelligence has significant potential for energy savings by enhancing weather forecasting and vehicle maintenance, as well as facilitating communication between homes, workplaces, and transportation [13].

S. M. Nguea writes that higher oil prices may encourage the adoption of energy-saving behaviors, such as using public transportation or investing in energy-efficient appliances. Oil prices are hindering urbanization by reducing carbon emissions in both low- and high-emission countries [14].

R. V. Ionescu et al. test a model capable of quantifying development and risks facing the oil industry at the European level. According to the authors, using this tool, it is possible to identify key elements of energy policy that can bring valuable clarification in the context of the industry's new orientations towards green energy and the reduction of polluting fuels [15].

H. Awijen et al. analyze oil prices from December 2007 to December 2021. The authors propose to predict prices using deep learning methods [16].

B. Vasić et al. consider the security and development challenges facing Central Asian countries beyond 2022. The authors believe that the countries of Central Asia have certain features in terms of sustainable development, where energy security, corruption, and government efficiency can be considered the most significant problems [17].

Thus, the analysis and assessment of changes in the energy structure in the energy market involve studying economic, environmental, geopolitical, and technological

aspects. At the same time, it is essential to analyze historical data, current trends, and predict future changes in the structure of supply and demand, as well as in energy production and the utilization of technologies. It is relevant to create models that will help predict possible ways of developing the energy structure and assess the consequences of various strategies. The results of these scientific developments should be proposed as strategies for businesses, governments, and international organizations to help them adapt to new conditions and minimize negative consequences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material for the study was research and analytical reports on energy, climate policy and sustainable development, published in scientific journals and reports of international organizations: Sustainability Science, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Nature Energy, Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Asia Europe Journal, Environmental Chemistry Letters Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Journal of Petroleum Exploration and Production Technology, et al.

The following methods of scientific research are employed in this work: literature analysis, statistical data analysis (including graphical analysis of dynamics and structure), comparison, and generalization. Based on scientific publications analysis, the concept of energy structure is considered, and the types of energy structures are summarized in the context of their historical development. In practical terms, based on BP statistics, the Energy Institute has identified the role of the 2021-2022 energy crisis in altering the global energy structure and its impact on the development of the worldwide energy market. Statistical data for the period from 1965 to 2022 were used in the work.

RESULTS

Role of the energy crisis of 2021-2022 in changing the global energy structure

To assess the role of the 2021-2022 energy crisis in the shift in the energy structure and its impact on the development of the global energy market, this work conducts its research based on statistics from the Energy Institute, previously published by BP p.l.c. [18].

To identify the main trends in the global energy market, this work analyzed the dynamics of energy consumption worldwide by continent. The dynamics of global energy consumption growth are shown in Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, global energy consumption reached a volume of over 600 EJ by the end of 2022. At the same time, the growth rate of the indicator is positive, although it typically decreases during crisis periods. Thus, the average annual growth rate for 1965-2022 is 102.4%. For comparison, in the XXI century (from 2000 to 2022), this figure was 101.9%.

Figure 1 Dynamics of global energy consumption for 1965-2022, EJ

Source: compiled by the authors based on the study data [19]

The level of diversification in the global energy market, categorized by energy sources, is assessed in Table 1.

Table 1

Dynamics of the structure of global energy consumption by types of energy sources for 1965-2022

Years	1965	1975	1985	1995	2005	2015	2020	2021	2022
Oil, EJ	64.79	114.29	121.2	142.06	168.8	183.47	174.99	184.86	190.69
Natural Gas, EJ	22.69	41.98	58.54	75.98	98.78	125.24	138.97	146.41	141.89
Coal, EJ	58.1	64.89	86.36	93.48	130.26	157.21	152.04	160.43	161.47
Nuclear Energy, EJ	0.26	3.78	15.21	23.72	27.39	23.96	24.4	25.33	24.13
Hydroelectricity, EJ	9.83	15.42	21.07	26.44	30.01	37.61	41.21	40.4	40.68
Renewable Energy, EJ	0.2	0.39	0.88	1.73	3.97	16.62	31.01	35.85	40.86
Biofuels, EJ	0.04	0.04	0.24	0.47	0.87	3.28	3.87	4.13	4.32
Primary Energy, EJ	155.91	240.79	303.5	363.88	460.08	547.39	566.49	597.41	604.04

Energy intensity, EJ/ GDP	7.91	7.69	7.12	6.53	5.75	4.88	4.56	4.54	4.45
Energy intensity growth rate,%	-	-2.78	-7.41	-8.29	-11.94	-15.13	-6.56	-0.44	-1.98
Absolute change in energy intensity growth rate,%	-	-	-4.63	-0.87	-3.66	-3.19	8.57	6.12	-1.54

Source: compiled by the authors based on the study data [20]

According to Table 2, the global energy market shows a stable trend towards increasing diversification in terms of energy sources. In particular, there is a clear downward trend in the share of oil in global energy consumption. Notably, the global maximum (49.22%) of oil's share in world energy consumption was reached in 1973. By the end of 2022, its share decreased to 31.57%.

At the same time, the share of natural gas reached its maximum by the end of the study period. The share of natural gas reached its global maximum (24.53%) in the crisis year of 2020 and slightly decreased by the end of 2022 (to 23.49%) [21]. The barriers to the growth of the natural gas market in 2022 were both the situation around Ukraine [22] (at that time one of the largest countries providing gas transportation services) and explosions on the Nord Stream 1 and 2 gas pipelines, which are a manifestation of unfair competition in the European natural gas market [23].

Furthermore, the dynamics of energy intensity in the global economy were assessed as a key indicator of the worldwide energy market. The results of this evaluation are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Energy intensity dynamics 1965-2022, %

Source: compiled by the authors based on the study data [24]

As shown in Figure 2, the following conclusions can be drawn for 1965-1987. The global energy market during this period was characterized by a high degree of volatility. One of the key indicators of market instability was increased energy intensity of the world economy, observed in 1969, 1970, 1978, 1984, and 1989. These spikes reflect periods when more energy was required to produce a unit of GDP, suggesting inefficiencies or disruptions in the energy system. Furthermore, prior to 1987, the growth rate of energy intensity exhibited greater fluctuations, as evidenced by comparative analysis with the more stable trends observed after 1987.

Regarding the impact of the 2021-2022 energy crisis, the decline in the energy intensity growth rate observed in 2022 historically occurred only during periods of pronounced energy market volatility. In particular, the decline recorded in 1980 significantly exceeded the 2022 figure, while the decrease in 1971 was slightly higher.

Further, an assessment was made of the dynamics of prices for the main types of fuel: oil, natural gas, and coal. It should be clarified that when conducting such an assessment, differences in prices were taken into account depending on the brand (for oil) and hubs (for natural gas and coal). Additionally, the time horizon for different fuels varies because the Energy Institute has not published price statistics outside the study period.

The results of this assessment on natural gas price dynamics are presented in Figure 3, from which several conclusions can be drawn.

Figure 3 Dynamics of natural gas prices for the period 1984-2022, USD US/MMBtu
Source: compiled by the authors based on the study data [25]

Clear manifestation of the energy crisis 2021-2022 is a sharp (abrupt) rise in prices for basic fuels. At the same time, the most significant growth is observed in the natural gas market. Moreover, as shown in Figure 3, not all regional natural gas markets experienced a sharp price increase in 2022. In particular, in the US and Canadian markets, the rise in natural gas prices in 2022 was not critical and did not lead to a global peak. It should be noted that the cost of natural gas Japan CIF (LNG) also did not show a significant increase; however, no information is available for this market in 2022.

The most significant jump in natural gas prices in 2022 occurred in the Netherlands market. The Asian market also showed comparable equal price growth, albeit slightly weaker. The German and UK markets also faced a sharp increase in natural gas prices.

A similar situation is observed in the coal market, although the crisis was less pronounced here. Reaching global highs is noted in the markets of Europe, the USA, and Japan. It should be noted that the Chinese market is in relative stagnation by the end of the research period; however, it is necessary to acknowledge the lack of data for 2022. In our opinion, the energy crisis of 2021-2022 affected the oil market; although the rise in prices in 2022 is observed across all oil brands.

To identify the connection between the global energy crisis and emerging trends in the formation of a new energy structure, we will examine the dynamics of the share of renewable energy in the worldwide energy generation structure, within the context of the world's regions (see Table 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of WEI share in the structure of energy balances by regions
of the world, %

Region	2000	2005.	2010.	2015	2022	Growth (+/-), percentage points
Europe	20.1	19.8	25.2	33.6	43.0	+22.9
CIS	17.9	17.9	16.3	15.6	19.7	+1.8
North America	15.5	15.5	16.7	20.3	28.1	+12.6
Latin America	61.6	58.8	57.3	51.8	64.7	+3.1
Asia	13.3	13.7	15.7	19.7	26.9	+13.6
Pacific Ocean	18.9	18.0	18.7	23.7	38.6	+19.7
Africa	17.9	17.0	17.2	18.0	25.0	+7.1
Middle East	1.7	4.3	2.0	1.7	3.2	+1.5

Source: compiled by the authors based on the study data [26]

Over the past two decades, the share of energy generation from WEI increased significantly worldwide. The most significant increase is recorded in Europe (+22.9%) and in the Pacific region (+19.6%), while the least is in the Middle East (+1.5%) and in the CIS (+1.8%). The largest share of renewable energy in total energy production is observed in Latin America (64.7%) and in Europe (43.0%). The share of renewable energy is exceptionally high in countries with ample hydropower resources, such as Brazil, Canada, Norway, New Zealand, and Sweden (more than 65% of total production). At the same time, the value of the specific gravity indicator depends on factors such as availability of renewable energy sources and generation costs from these sources, availability and price of fossil fuels, the level of economic development of countries included in the corresponding group, and the political factor. For instance, the low share of renewable energy sources in the Middle East is due to the presence and cheapness of the extraction of carbon raw materials and the absence of the need to increase energy generation due to renewable energy sources shortly; in the CIS, it was due to structural transformation of its economic systems, accompanied by frequent and prolonged crises that did not contribute to renewable energy sources development and use. In Europe, high indicators of both specific gravity and growth are due to dependence on imports of fossil fuels, the lack of own deposits in most countries, and political motives (a decrease in dependence on Russian raw materials). It is also possible to observe fluctuations in the increase indicators of specific gravity of renewable energy sources during the analyzed period. For example, in Latin America, a negative increase in the share of renewable energy was recorded until 2015; in other regions (except Europe, Asia, and North America), the increase was also variable. In general, worldwide, as indicated earlier, a positive increase was recorded at the end of the study period, which may be attributed to the impact of the global energy crisis. Reduced supply of natural gas in regional markets, increased cost, and high volatility of prices for this energy resource (recorded from the end of 2021) led to financial contamination of the energy industries of various countries. Following the rise in natural gas prices, prices for coal, solid fuels, and refined products also increased, leading to a surge in energy costs. All this strengthened the position of renewable energy sources in global energy production.

In these conditions, Russia faced the need to rethink its role and place in the emerging new global energy structure. On the one hand, Russia continues to play a key role in supplying traditional energy resources, primarily natural gas,

to international markets. However, given the global trends in decarbonization and accelerated development of renewable energy sources, Russia is forced to adapt its energy strategy to new realities by intensifying the growth rate of green energy. Programs are being implemented to support wind and solar power, while hydroelectric power plants are being expanded. Steps are also being taken to develop promising technologies, such as geothermal and hydrogen energy. In this context, Russia, with its significant resources, scientific and technical potential, and extensive cross-border energy infrastructure, can become one of the leading countries in the emerging global energy market [27].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this article, a study was conducted to assess the role of the 2021-2022 energy crisis in the change in the energy structure. The characteristics of energy patterns in a historical context are presented. The world community is currently experiencing a transitional energy structure, characterized by a weakening of oil's position and an increasing role for natural gas and other types of fuel. The authors also concluded that strengthening of the policy positions for energy transition and decarbonization of energy systems, which is observed under the influence of the global energy crisis, is a prerequisite for forming a new energy structure based on the use of renewable energy sources and hydrogen raw materials.

It was established that the energy crisis of 2021-2022 most significantly impacted the natural gas markets in Europe and Asia. At the same time, a steady downward trend can be observed in the share of oil consumption within the global energy market. This decline is largely offset by a rising share of natural gas and renewable energy sources. In our view, this shift reflects the broader implications of the 2021-2022 energy crisis which serves as a precursor to an impending transformation of the global energy structure. Summarizing this analysis, we propose the following thesis: "The ongoing transformation of the global energy structure is marked by a gradual transition from an oil-dominated model toward one increasingly centered on renewable energy, a shift expected to unfold over the coming decades".

Thus, the emphasis on solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal energy is apparent. There are also excellent prospects for creating smart grids and systems that enable more efficient distribution and use of energy. Scientific research aiming to develop new materials, technologies, and standards that will help reduce energy consumption

without losing quality of life or production efficiency is also relevant. At the same time, it is essential to strengthen cooperation between countries in the energy field, including the exchange of technologies, joint research, and the development of international standards.

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